

DYES DERIVED FROM ACENAPHTHENEQUINONE. PART IX. ISOMERIC (METHYL)THIONAPHTHENE-ACENAPHTHYLENE-INDIGOS

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The relation between the colour and the chemical constitution of all the isomeric (methyl)thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos has been deduced.

In Part VIII of this series (Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **20**, 37) the preparation of a few 2-(7-methyl)thionaphthene-8'-acenaphthylene-indigos was described. But their depth of colour and subsequently their relations with those of the corresponding isomeric dyes of the 4-, 5-, and 6-methyl series (Guha, *ibid.*, 1933, **10**, 682; 1936, **13**, 94; 1938, **15**, 23) were not established which was the primary object with which the investigation was at first undertaken.

Now the absorption spectra of the parent compound of this 7-methyl series and its methoxy derivative have been taken. The absorption curves (Figs. 2 and 3) have been drawn by a microphotometer and their absorption maxima calculated. For the purpose of a comparative study, Ciba Scarlet G has also been prepared, its absorption curve (Fig. 1) drawn and the absorption maxima found. A comparison of colour and of the dyeing shades of the vat dyes of this 7-methyl series and Ciba Scarlet G and of the absorption maxima of some of these with those of the corresponding isomeric 4-, 5-, and 6-methyl compounds indicates that the influence of Me group in the 7-position of the thionaphthene nucleus of Ciba Scarlet G is also to produce "hypsochromic effect" (Table I). Moreover, it is evident that there are three positions, namely, 4-, 6-, and 7- in the thionaphthene ring of Ciba Scarlet G where the effect of substitution by Me group is to lighten the colour of the mother compound and the maximum lightening effect is produced by substitution in 6-position. But there is only one position, *viz.*, 5, where similar substitution produces "bathochromic" effect.

Therefore, the depth of colour of the various isomeric (methyl) thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos may be now arranged in the order : 5-methyl dye > 4-methyl dye > 7-methyl dye > 6-methyl dye. The depth of colour of the parent compound, Ciba Scarlet G is next to that of the 5-methyl dye. The author has not taken into consideration the values against shorter absorption maxima as it is quite clear from the colour and the dyeing shades of these 7-methyl dyes that each of them is deeper in colour than the corresponding compound belonging to the 6-methyl series and this view has been confirmed by the quantitative measurement of the depth of colour of some of these dyes.

It may be pointed here that the author's observation with regard to the relation between the depth of colour and the constitution of all the isomeric (methyl)thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos is not exactly the same as what was noticed in the case of another series of asymmetrical dyes, the isomeric indole-(methyl) thionaphthene-indigos and also the symmetrical dyes, the isomeric dimethylthioindigos, where the maximum lightening effect is produced by Me substitution in the 7-position of the thionaphthene ring of the molecule of the dye (Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **21**, 87). But, in all the three series, the general observation is the same in the sense that there is only one position in the thionaphthene ring where the introduction of the Me group produced deepening effect and three different positions where similar substitution lightened the colour of the parent compound.

On an examination of the absorption curves of Ciba Scarlet G and the various isomeric (methyl)thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos (Figs. 1, 2, and 3; also see Part VI of this series) it will appear, that the absorption bands in the case of 5-methyl compounds which are the deepest

FIG. 1

Curve 1 refers to 2-thionaphthylene-8'-acenaphthylene-indigo (Cuba Scarlet G).

FIG. 2

Curve 1 refers to 2-(7-methyl)-thionaphthylene-8'-acenaphthylene-indigo.

FIG. 3

Curve 1 refers to 2-(7-methyl)-thionaphthylene-8'-acenaphthylene-indigo.

of all in this series are much broader and their depth of absorption is also greater than that of the 4-, 7-, and 6-methyl isomerides. The head of the absorption band of the 5-methyl-dye is shifted much towards the red end of the spectrum and then follow those of the 4-, 7-, and 6-methyl compounds respectively. This is in agreement with the conclusion drawn qualitatively.

It is also noticed that of the different substituents present in the acenaphthene part of the molecule of the dye, the inert group, OMe deepens the shade of the dyes more than Cl or Br atom. But this value of the methoxy dyes is marred by the fact that they offer much resistance to reduction in the hydrosulphite vat in consequence of which their true shades could not be obtained on cotton by repeated trial.

The detailed study in this acenaphthenequinone series has enabled the author to select a few vat colours of deep but pleasant and attractive shade and good fastness.

TABLE I

T = Thionaphthene ; A = Acenaphthylene-indigo.

Compounds.	Absorption maxima.	Compound.	Absorption maxima.
2-T-8'-A (Ciba Scarlet G)	... 4775 Å	2-(4-Methyl)-T-8'-(1'-methoxy)-A	... 4810 Å
2-(4-Methyl)-T-8'-A	... 4735	2-(5-Methyl)-T-8'-(1'-methoxy)-A	... 4995
2-(5-Methyl)-T-8'-A	... 4985	2-(6-Methyl)-T-8'-(1'-methoxy)-A	... 4783
2-(6-Methyl)-T-8'-A	... 4622	2-(7-Methyl)-T-8'-(1'-methoxy)-A	... { 4790 (longer) 4685 (shorter)
2-(7-Methyl)-T-8'-A	... { 4710 (longer) 4350 (shorter)		

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